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Autologous versus allogeneic transfusion in large-scale orthopedic surgery

Mirka Lukic-Sarkanovic, Ivica Lalic, Ljiljana Gvozdenovic, Zoran Gojkovic, Nemanja Gvozdenovic

Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

Abstract

Aim: The aim of this study was to prove efficiency, safety, cost-effectiveness, and (indirect) impact on the patients' outcome of autologous transfusion in patients who had the total hip replacement surgery.

Methods: During the controlled, prospective, randomised study we compared two groups of patients who had the total prosthesis implanted in their hip, in total there were 84 of them. The first group consisted of the patients who received the transfusion of other people's (allogeneic) blood (n=47) and the other one consisted of the patients whose blood was collected perioperatively (their own, autologous blood) (n=37). Transfusion trigger for both groups was haemoglobin level of 90 g/l.

Results: In the group of patients whose blood was collected perioperatively 32,43% received the transfusion of allogeneic blood, as opposed to the control group in which 95,74% received the transfusion of allogeneic blood ($p \leq 0,01$). For the group of patients whose blood was collected the number of days spent in hospital was 6,78, while for the control group it was 7,28 days.

Conclusion: Our conclusion is that during the total hip replacement surgery perioperative autologous blood collection is very effective measure in reducing consumption of allogeneic blood, reduces likelihood of complications related to application of allogeneic transfusion (indirect), and have positive effect on patient's overall clinical outcome.

Key words: Transfusion, allogeneic, autologous, blood, hip replacement.

Introduction

Total hip replacement (THR) surgery is one of the most frequent and extensive procedures in orthopaedic surgery, accompanied with some serious complications. Perioperative blood loss is one of the most serious losses, so it is vital to recognize and tre-

at such losses properly. The timely and precise treatment of perioperative blood losses has an impact of the patients' outcome and the quality of postoperative recovery(1,2,3). The transfusion of allogeneic blood carries along certain risks, such as allergic reactions, anaphylaxis, hemolytic reactions, transmissible diseases, transfusion related lung injury (TRALI), graft-versus-host disease, etc. (4,5,6,9,11). In the past few decades a lot of effort has been made to find a solution to the problems connected with allogeneic transfusion. One of the alternatives is autologous blood transfusion, which is widely accepted as probably the only true alternative for the allogeneic blood. The justification for the use of this alternative method could be found in a certain level of morbidity and mortality which accompanies allogeneic blood transfusions. (7, 10, 12, 13, 17).

The autologous blood transfusion is a collection and re-infusion (transfusion) of the patient's own blood or blood components before, during or after surgical procedure. So the donor and recipient of the blood is the same person. Although not completely risk-free, autologous blood is the safest blood donation (8).

According to the American Association of Blood Banks the most important strategies for blood donation are: preoperative autologous donation, acute normovolemic hemodilution, and perioperative blood salvage. (15, 16).

Perioperative blood salvage is intraoperative collection by aspiration from the operative fields and postoperative collection of the blood from the wound drains (14).

Autologous transfusion is indicated in certain surgeries when we expect to have major blood losses. The prerequisite for this procedure is that there is no wound or systematic infection and normal hemoglobin levels in the patient's blood.

Total hip replacement surgery is one of the most serious operations in orthopaedic surgery. Frequently accompanied with serious intraope-

rative and postoperative bleeding, so autologous blood salvation takes place from the collection by aspiration from the operative fields and from the wound drains in the perioperative period (8,10).

Our goal was to improve our everyday clinical practice, and this study will contribute to our better understanding of perioperative blood loss and its treatment in THR surgery with the ultimate goal to affect patients' outcome in a positive way.

The aim of this study was to prove efficiency, safety, cost – effectiveness, and impact on the patient's outcome of autologous transfusion.

Methods

This was a single-centre (Clinic for Orthopaedic Surgery and Traumatology-Clinical Center of Voivodina, Novi Sad), prospective, randomised, controlled study conducted on the patients undergoing THR surgery.

After review and approval by the Local Research Ethics Committee, we obtained informed consent and studied 84 patients, during the period of three months during 2010. Patients were randomly placed in two treatment groups, the first one receiving allogeneic blood (n=47), and the second receiving autologous blood (n=37).

The transfusion trigger for the group that received allogeneic blood was of 90g/l (1, 2, 3, and 4). We chose this value for the hemoglobin trigger because the majority of our patients are elderly people, usually with comorbidities. For the group that received autologous (their own) transfusion, blood was collected perioperatively, from the collection by aspiration from the operative fields (intraoperatively) and from the wound drains postoperatively during the period of four hours. The minimal amount of drained blood was ≥ 200 ml for the process to be successful (according to the manufacturer's manual and our experience). We used *Cell Saver* (*Haemonetics 5+*, USA) apparatus; the blood was collected, processed and re-infused to the patients. For this purpose we had allocated trained anesthesiology technician. One unit of autologous blood was 250 ml.

Hemoglobin levels were measured preoperatively and postoperatively after 6, 12 and 24 hours for all patients. Preoperatively, as well as 24 hours after the surgery, we measured APTT (activated partial thromboplastin time) and PT (prothrombin time).

The THR surgery was performed as a routine. The patients underwent general (balanced) anesthesia or spinal anesthesia, which have been standardized in terms of drugs and procedures.

Intraoperative blood losses were measured as losses in gauze and as losses in the hood.

Postoperative blood losses were measured as losses in wound drains during the period of first 48 hrs after the surgery for all patients, accompanied with the clinical examination of the patients.

We recorded the time when patients sat, stood, walked and had their meal for the first time after the surgery, by this we indirectly measured the quality of postoperative recovery. The length of staying in hospital was also recorded. The exclusion criteria for this study were: patients with septic complications, multiple fractures, malignancy, ASA physical status classification IV or more, hemiarthroplasty and all patients with incomplete data.

All data were analyzed in SPSS 16.0 software package. All frequencies, percentages, and median standard deviation were calculated. Binary variables were compared by χ^2 test, continuous variable were compared by Fisher's Exact test and the t-test. A statistically significant difference was defined as p value $< 0, 05$. All data (text, tables, and charts) were arranged by *Microsoft Word 2003* and *Microsoft Excel 2003*.

Results

Out of 84 patients, 53 were women and 31 were men. For the purpose of this study we compared the age, gender, ASA status, comorbidities, chronic NSAID/aspirin use, anesthesia method, the type of prosthetic material, perioperative levels of hemoglobin, hematocrit, trombocyte count, the mechanism of hemostasis, blood losses, the number of blood units of allogeneic and autologous blood per each patient, the time when patients sat, stood, walked and had their meals for the first time after the surgery, as well as the length of staying in hospital, in order to see how they affected the outcome of these patients.

In both groups the majority of patients were women 53 (63, 1%).

American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) status ASA III patients were most frequent in both groups – 45 patients in total (53, 6%). There were no ASA I patients.

Table 1. Patient's characteristics

	Autologous group	Allogeneic group	p value
Mean age	64,7(41-85)	63,0(39-80)	0,05
Gender			
male	12(32,4%)	19(40,4%)	
female	25(67,6%)	28(59,6%)	
Methods of anesthesia			
general	14(37,8%)	16(34,0%)	0,05
spinal	23(62,2%)	31(66,0%)	0,05
Type of knee prosthesis			
cemented	27(73,0%)	19(40,4%)	0,05
cementless	10(27,0%)	28(59,6%)	

Table 2. Preoperative and postoperative values of haemoglobin, hematocrit, trombocytes, APTT and PT

	Autologous group	Allogeneic group	p value
Hemoglobin (g/l)			
preoperatively	134,24	134,43	>0,05
postoperatively:			
6 hrs	115,76	119,68	>0,05
24 hrs	106,24	112,74	>0,05
48 hrs	97,41	109,37	<0,01
Hematocrit (g/l)			
preoperativno	39,43	38,82	>0,05
postoperatively:			
6 hrs	33,81	34,76	>0,05
24 hrs	30,86	32,79	>0,05
48 hrs	28,31	31,41	<0,01
Trombocytes			
preoperatively	256,73	251,04	>0,05
postoperatively:			
6 hrs	191,24	199,66	>0,05
24 hrs	181,95	192,98	>0,05
48 hrs	164,81	191,89	>0,05
APTT*			
preoperatively	0,973(0,75-1,41)	0,932(0,79-1,15)	>0,05
after 24 hrs	0,959(0,57- 1,45)	0,965(0,83-1,26)	>0,05
PT *			
preoperatively	0,958(0,10-1,36)	0,991(0,83-1,17)	>0,05
after 24 hrs	1,119(0,89-1,52)	0,999(0,10-1,23)	>0,01
Blood losses			
intraoperatively	802,70(300- 1500)	800,00(400-1500)	>0,05
postoperatively:			
after 6 hrs	481,08(100-1100)	433,40(100-1050)	>0,05
after 24 hrs	264,71(50-700)	404,26(150-1250)	>0,01
after 48 hrs	170,83(50-400)	240,54(100-450)	>0,05

* APTT (activated partial thromboplastin time) and PT (prothrombin time)

The majority of patients received spinal anesthesia - 54 patients (64,3%), and 30 patients (35,7%) received general anesthesia.

Comorbidities were very frequent, 64 patients (76,2%), in both groups, had some comorbidities, 20 patients (23, 8%) had none.

Almost all patients in both groups used some Aspirin or NSAIDs, only three patients did not use any of these drugs. When we compared hemoglobin and hematocrit levels measured postoperatively, there was a significant difference after 48 hrs in favour of the allogeneic group.

Table 3. Number of blood units in autologous and allogeneic group

	Autologous group	Allogeneic group
Allogeneic blood (units)		
1 unit	7(58,3%)	2(4,4%)
2 units	4(33,3%)	31(68,9%)
> 3 units	1(8,3%)	12(26,7%)
Autologous blood (units)		
1 unit	13(35,1%)	0
2 units	21(56,8%)	0
3 units	2(5,4%)	0
4 units	1(2,7%)	0

Values of PT 24 hrs postoperatively were higher and showed a significant difference in the autologous group. That can be explained by blood processing in the autologous transfusion method. In this process only „washed“ eritrocites are reinfused back to the patient, and the rest of plasma and coagulation factors, with cell detritus, anticoagulants, normal saline and bone micro fragments are disposed and wasted.

The transfusion triggers in both groups were hemoglobin levels of ≤ 90 g/l.

Out of 37 patients in the autologous group, 12 patients (32,44%) received the additional transfusion of allogeneic blood (n= 18 units of allogeneic blood), so that means that 25 patients (67,56%) received only their own (autologous) blood.

In the allogeneic (control) group 45 patients received allogeneic blood, 31 patients (68, 9%), patients received 2 units of allogeneic blood, 2 patients (4, 4%) received 1 unit of allogeneic blood, 12 patients (26,7%) received more than three units of allogeneic blood. Only two patient did not receive allogeneic blood.

In the autologous group the majority of patients received one or two units of autologous blood (n= 34 patients), two patients got 3 units of autologous

transfusion and only one patients got 4 units of autologous transfusion.

The time when patients sat, stood, walked and had their meal for the first time after the surgery served as the indirect indicator of quality of postoperative recovery. In the autologous group patients sat, stood and walked earlier ($p < 0,001$) than in the allogeneic group. In this group, patients were able to eat (their first meal) 17,45 hrs earlier than in the allogeneic (control) group ($p < 0,001$).

An average hospital stay in the autologous group was 6,78 days, and in the allogeneic (control group) 7,28 days. The final decision about when the patient was going to be discharged from hospital was on attending the surgeon, and our team, being researchers, had no impact on it.

We analysed deep venous thrombosis (DVT), pulmonary tromboembolic complications, sepsis, wound infection and major cardiovascular complications. Perioperative complications were rare and there were only two cases in the allogeneic (control) group. One was the wound infection and other was chest pain with no major morbidity. In the autologous group there were no complications.

Discussion

The average patient in our study was female, 66.5 years old, ASA III status with comorbidities and chronic usage of NSAID's or Aspirin. These data are consistent with the fact that indications for THR surgery are degenerative diseases of the hip, which are painful states, more frequent in elderly females(18,19).

We think that the most important result of our study is one showing that autologous transfusion is very effective measure in reducing consumption of allogeneic blood. In the allogeneic (control) group 95.74% of patients postoperatively received allogeneic blood transfusion. In the au-

Table 4. Postoperative recovery

	Autologous group	Allogeneic group	p value
Postoperative recovery (hrs)			
sitting	10,22(8-24)	24,00(24-24)	<0,01
standing	17,24(12-24)	24,26(24-36)	<0,01
walking	18,86(12-48)	27,13(24-48)	<0,01
eating	9,68(4-24)	27,13(24-48)	<0,01
Hospital stay (days)	6,78(3-13)	7,28(1-23)	>0,05

tologous group of patients 32,43% received allogeneic blood transfusion, which is almost tri times reduction in the consumption of this type of blood (12, 20, 21).

There is a shortage of blood everywhere in the world, the same situation is in Serbia, so every method that reduces consumption of allogeneic blood is of vital importance. In our country blood donation is voluntary, which leads to a wrong conclusion that blood itself is free of charge. The process of making blood and blood components safe is an expensive part of blood production. The analysis of cost-effectiveness of autologous transfusion was not the aim of this study, and it is very hard to analyse it because there is no official data about the cost of blood in our country. Today, blood and blood products are safer than ever, but still there are some known morbidities and mortalities connected to allogeneic transfusion, so by reducing its consumption we reduce those risks. Autologous transfusion has its own costs, but an additional justification for its usage can be found in the improved safety of this method.

The patients in the autologous group lost significantly less blood in general. There is also a significant difference in the postoperative blood loss between two groups 24 and 48 hrs after the surgery; the patients in autologous group lost less blood too.

Postoperative recovery after THR surgery is multifactorial, but there is a statistically significant difference in the speed and quality of postoperative recovery in the autologous group, accompanied with fewer complications (22). Unfortunately, we were not able to follow the patients and complication rate after hospital dismissal, and we know that such data (collected for the first six months postoperatively at least) could be very important for the introspection of this method itself. Staying in hospital is reduced in this group of patients.

However, this study has some limitations. In spite of the local study recommendations for the transfusion trigger of 90g/l, sometimes this strict protocol was not followed and some surgeons are still reluctant to apply these recommendations since they consider them too low. This fact maybe explains higher hemoglobin levels in the allogeneic (control) group, because there is a strict protocol appliance in the autologous group controlled by the anesthesia technician and anesthesiologist.

The length of staying in hospital is reduced in the autologous group of patients. There is no consensus in our clinic about how long patients should be hospitalized after THR surgery, so this decision was made by consulting the surgeon as well.

Conclusion

Autologous blood transfusion is a effective method for reducing allogeneic blood use, as well as for preventing of allogeneic blood induced side effects and complications. This research confirms clear benefit of this particular method.

When we compare our results with recent studies, we can conclude that they are consistent.

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Corresponding Author

Ljiljana Gvozdenovic,
Clinical Center of Vojvodina,
Novi Sad,
Serbia,

E-mail: profgvozdenovic2010@hotmail.com